

Maqam Sidi Sahbi

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Religious Place, Sufi Order, Tunisia

It is a Maqam where one of the companions of the Messenger of God is buried. It is located in the city of Kairouan. It is a sacred place for Muslims for the holiness of the companion.

Date Range: 1400 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Kairouan

Region tags: Tunisia

Kairouan is the first Islamic religious city in North Africa. The Maqam of Sidi Sahbi is linked to this area

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: كان مقام سيدي الصحبي في عين جلولة وهو المكان الذي قتل فيه. وعين جلولة مكان مرتبط بعين ماء. ثم نقل في العصر الحديث إلى القبروان لرمزية المدينة

Reference: "البحروني, هدى. "المؤسسة الدينية بين المقدس والديني مقام ابي زمعة البلوي نموذجاً". <https://www.mominoun.com/>, n.d.. <https://www.mominoun.com/pdf/2015-09/56027880e4a9a938358495.pdf>.

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: The shrine is distinguished by its blessed grave

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - Yes

- ↳ A group of features:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
 - No

- ↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
 - Worship
 - ↳ Worship:
 - Communal

- ↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
 - No

- ↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In antiquity
 - More than once

- ↳ In modernity
- Post-Renaissance

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

- ↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
- No

- ↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
- No

Notes: L'être "surnaturel" dont on parle n'est autre que les esprits des "Salihin" (les hommes pieux)

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: المالكي، أبو بكر، رياض التّفوس، تحقيق بشير البكوش، مراجعة محمد العروسي المطوي، دار الغرب الإسلامي، بيروت، ط 2، 1994.
- Source 2: التليلي، العجيلي، الطرق الصوفية والاستعمار الفرنسي بالبلاد التونسية 1881-1939، طونوس، 1992.
- Source 3: الدباغ، أبو زيد عبد الرحمان، معالم الإيمان في معرفة أهل القيروان، نسخة الكترونية.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

- ↳ Type of feature
- Trackway or road-surface

Notes: On the main road at the entrance to the city from Tunis

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL:
<https://www.mominoun.com/articles/%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85%D8%A4%D8%B3%D8%B3%D8%A9-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AF%D9%8A%D9%86%D9%8A%D8%A9-%D8%A8%D9%8A%D9%86-%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85%D9%82%D8%AF%D8%B3-%D9%88%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AF%D9%86%D9%8A%D9%88%D9%8A-3143>

– Source 1 Description: دراسة أنثروبولوجية للمقدّس الديني وأثره الاجتماعي في القيروان

– Source 2 URL: <https://arbyy.com/detail998209123.html>

– Source 2 Description: معلومات عن المقام من حيث الهندسة والبناء

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BkxICi83ITQ>

– Source 1 Description: Vidéo à propos de Sidi Sahbi

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.afrigatenews.net/article/%D9%85%D9%82%D8%A7%D9%85-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B5%D8%AD%D8%A7%D8%A8%D9%8A-%D8%A3%D8%A8%D9%88%D8%B2%D9%85%D8%B9%D8%A9-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%A8%D9%84%D9%88%D9%8A-%D8%A8%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%82%D9%8A%D8%B1%D9%88%D8%A7%D9%86-%D9%85%D9%82%D8%B5%D8%AF-%D9%84%D9%84%D8%B2%D9%8A%D8%A7%D8%B1%D8%A9-%D9%88-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AA%D8%A8%D8%B1%D9%83/>

– Source 2 Description: article concernant le marabout Sidi Sahbi

– Source 3 URL: <https://www.elbalad.news/4084831>

– Source 3 Description: Un article qui s'intéresse de l'art du Marbre dans la Zaouia de Sidi Sahbi

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

Notes: Les compagnons du Prophète

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Notes: شهد المقام ترميمات كثيرة عبر الزمن

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Reference: "الجوادي, إبراهيم. "معالم دينية - مقام الصحابي الجليل أبي زمعة البلوي بالقيروان". Facebook, September 11, 2020. <https://www.facebook.com/watch/?v=802953020452731>.

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:
Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?
– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:
– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:
A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.
– Yes

↳ Specify
– King or emperor
– Other [specify]: Au début il était une tombe vénérée par les musulmans puit le roi Hammouda Pacha en 1663

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:
– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:
– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:
– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:
– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:
– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:
– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:
– Other [specify]: Thanksgiving and expression of devotion

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

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- Source 1: المالكي، أبو بكر، رياض التّفوس، تحقيق بشير البكوش، مراجعة محمد العروسي المطوي، دار الغرب الإسلامي، بيروت، ط 2، 1994.
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Notes: شهد المقام ترميمات كثيرة عبر الزمن

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

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↳ In antiquity

– More than once

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

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Notes: L'être "surnaturel" dont on parle n'est autre que les esprits des "Salihin" (les hommes pieux)

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Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

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Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Des versets du saint Coran

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Surtout des calligraphies

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: Des tableaux avec des versets du Coran, un marbre qui expose l'arbre généalogique

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– No

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: Marbre, Cristal, Plastique

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Les tapis, les draps, les drapeaux, les tableaux....

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

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– Yes [specify]: Les tapis, les draps, les drapeaux, les tableaux...

Decoration

Is decoration present:

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–Other [specify]: Des versets du saint Coran

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–Other [specify]: Surtout des calligraphies

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: Des tableaux avec des versets du Coran, un marbre qui expose l'arbre

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– No

Notes: Il est connu que des femmes viennent au Maqam pour avoir un époux ou des enfants

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– No

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: L'esprit du Sidi Sahbi est présent

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

–optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Yes

↳ Birth

– No

↳ Transition to adulthood

– Yes

Notes: La circoncision, pour les habitants du Kairouan, se fait dans le Maqam

↳ Death

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Les fêtes du Mawlid Annabaoui (l'anniversaire du Prophète) sont les plus attirants pour le Maqam

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is divination present:

– Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

– No

↳ Divination through human communication:

– No

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:

– No

↳ Divination through non-living material:

–Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Le plomb chauffé dissout dans l'eau froid.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: L'esprit du compagnons du Prophète est présent

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: 1000-25000

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Une fois par an pendant le Mawlid Nabawi

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

- ↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Are they unquestionably good:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are they other:
 - Other [specify]: Dieu est unique et la présence est métaphorique

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

- ↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:
 - No

- ↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:
 - Yes

- ↳ Priests
 - No

- ↳ Local elites
 - Yes

↳ Private contributions

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Les habitants et les gens participent aux festivités

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

–Yes [specify]: Il y a des chambres spéciales pour les repas

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– No

↳ Healing magic

– No

↳ Cleansing

– Yes

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

↳ Expiation

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Une femme attache une partie d'un mouchoir à la fenêtre du maqam, demandant le mariage ou des enfants

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - No

Are festivals present:

- Yes

- ↳ Frequency of festivals
 - specify: Liés au Mawlid Annabawi

- ↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):
 - All members
 - Elites
 - Non-elites

- ↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:
 - No

- ↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:
 - number: 10000-100000

- ↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):
 - Yes

- ↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:
 - Elites
 - Non-elites

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

- No

Are material offerings present:

- No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

- No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– No

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Les réparations ne sont pas périodiques

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Dans le Maqam on trouve d'autres tombes lié par un certain lien avec le Maqam

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Dans le Maqam on trouve d'autres tombes lié par un certain lien avec le Maqam

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– I don't know

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: Dieu est unique et la présence est métaphorique

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Does the worship include sex acts/references:

– No

Notes: Il est connu que des femmes viennent au Maqam pour avoir un époux ou des enfants

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:
 - No
- ↳ Other:
 - Other [specify]: L'esprit du Sidi Sahbi est présent

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

- ↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
 - Yes
- ↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
 - Yes
- ↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
 - specify: 1000-25000

↳ How often do these rituals take place:
– specify: Une fois par an pendant le Mawlid Nabawi

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:
– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:
– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:
– No

Are material offerings present:
– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:
– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:
– Yes

↳ Is it required:
– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– No

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Les réparations ne sont pas périodiques

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Yes

↳ Birth

– No

↳ Transition to adulthood

– Yes

Notes: La circoncision, pour les habitants du Kairouan, se fait dans le Maqam

↳ Death

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Les fêtes du Mawlid Annabaoui (l'anniversaire du Prophète) sont les

plus attirants pour le Maqam

- ↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
 - No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

- ↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:
 - No

- ↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:
 - Yes

- ↳ Priests
 - No

- ↳ Local elites
 - Yes

- ↳ Private contributions
 - No

- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: Les habitants et les gens participent aux festivités

- ↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:
 - Yes [specify]: Il y a des chambres spéciales pour les repas

Are festivals present:

– Yes

- ↳ Frequency of festivals
 - specify: Liés au Mawlid Annabawi

- ↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

- All members
- Elites
- Non-elites

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

- No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

- number: 10000-100000

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

- Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

- Elites
- Non-elites

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

- Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the extra:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

- No

↳ Divination through human communication:

- No

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:

- No

↳ Divination through non-living material:

- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Le plomb chauffé dissout dans l'eau froid.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: L'esprit du compagnons du Prophète est présent

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– No

↳ Healing magic

– No

↳ Cleansing

– Yes

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

↳ Expiation

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Une femme attache une partie d'un mouchoir à la fenêtre du maqam, demandant le mariage ou des enfants

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– No

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

Notes: Dans les fêtes religieuses ou non religieuses (mariage, Circoncision).

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Yes

Notes: Parfois des colloques sur le tourisme religieux, l'écriture des contrat de mariage.

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

Notes: Le tombeau de Sidi Sahbi était dans un autre lieu qu' où il est aujourd'hui, il était à 'In Jloula (lieu appelé Source d'eau Jloula), près d'une source d'eau

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Le Maqam de Sidi Sahbi est lieu où les citadins de Kairouan viennent lui demander tout ce qu'il veulent il croient que c'est un lieu où Dieu accepte leur demande

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: On y trouve des écritures qui concernent le Maqam et autre écritures religieuses

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: oui dans les jours des fêtes religieuses surtout le jour du Mawlid Nabawi (le jour dans lequel le Prophète Mohammad est né)

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: oui dans les jours des fêtes religieuses surtout le jour du Mawlid Nabawi (le jour dans lequel le Prophète Mohammad est né)

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:
Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders
– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:
– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:
– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):
– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:
– Yes

Notes: Dans les fêtes religieuses ou non religieuses (mariage, Circoncision).

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:
– Yes

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):
– Yes

Notes: Parfois des colloques sur le tourisme religieux, l'écriture des contrat de mariage.

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):
– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

Notes: Le tombeau de Sidi Sahbi était dans un autre lieu qu' où il est aujourd'hui, il était à 'In Jloula (lieu appelé Source d'eau Jloula), près d'une source d'eau

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Le Maqam de Sidi Sahbi est lieu où les citoyens de Kairouan viennent lui demander tout ce qu'il veulent il croient que c'est un lieu où Dieu accepte leur demande

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: On y trouve des écritures qui concernent le Maqam et autre écritures religieuses

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